

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: ANYE****FIRST NAME: MURIEL NGUM****PROGRAM CODE: DIPH****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 6****INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did not use Zotero to insert references

The author used Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: 2%

The author used the following software: MSWord 365 MSO on Windows 10

QUIZ FOR COURSE INTERNATIONAL ACADEMIC WRITING (DOCTORATE)

1. Considering you are a writer, is it acceptable to directly copy and paste information from a source into your academic paper without proper citation if you change a few words?

No.¹

Yes.

Maybe.

Not sure.

2. What is the purpose of an abstract in an academic paper?

¹ Cleenewerck Laurent and Kabiru Gulma, *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1* (Bangui: Euclid University, 2021), 5.

- To provide a summary of the author's personal opinions.
 - To briefly describe the author's background.
 - To give an overview of the paper's main points and findings.²**
 - To make the dissertation lengthy.
3. In this course study material, we have learned it is relevant for a writer to consult and interact with existing publications, citing them correctly. If a writer decides to eliminate part of the literature that contradicts his/her research question, is this a good practice?
- No, the writer should never remove any literature that contradicts his research. Instead, this should be added and used in the discussion section.³**
 - Yes, the writer can if the supervisor agrees.
 - Yes, even without consulting with the supervisor.
 - Not sure.
4. What are the different components of a research dissertation?
- Final Dissertation, Concept Note, Thesis, and Proposal.
 - Dissertation, Dissertation Proposal, Dissertation Concept Note.

² Sampson James, *A Guide to Quantitative and Qualitative Dissertation Research* (Tallahassee: Florida State University, 2017), 7.

³ Bloomberg Linda Dale and Marie Volpe, *Completing your Qualitative Dissertation: A Road Map from Beginning to End* (Los Angeles: Columbia University, 2019), 151.

Dissertation Manuscript, Dissertation, Dissertation Concept Note, and Dissertation Prospectus.⁴

Dissertation, Dissertation Concept Note.

5. Which of the statements below is correct?

In a dissertation, the titles of tables are written at the bottom, while the titles of figures are at the top.

Numbers between 1-10 are written in figures, while numbers from 11 and above are written in words.

When discussing the results, the writer can decide to interact with a few citations used in the literature that are in with his/her findings.

The most reliable authority for spelling is the Merriam-Webster.⁵

6. Select the most appropriate response below. While there are many types of essays, an academic essay seeks to:

Provide answers to hypotheses, aiming to communicate ideas based on evidence.⁶

Showcase the achievements of a particular writer.

Point out relevant publications.

Provide a convincing case in response to a prompt or inquiry.

⁴ James, *A Guide to Quantitative and Qualitative Dissertation Research*, 2.

⁵ Turabian Kate L., *A Manual for Writers of Term Papers, Theses, and Dissertations* (Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2018), 302.

⁶ EUCLID, *ACA-401-ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*, 7.

7. What is the purpose of a literature review in an academic paper?
- To present the author's original research findings.
 - To summarize and synthesize existing research on the topic.⁷**
 - To include personal anecdotes related to the topic.
 - To provide a detailed methodology for the study.
8. Which of the statements below is correct when writers use British English?
- Gram should be used and not gramme.⁸**
 - Metre for measuring instrument.
 - Meter for length.
 - All the above.
9. Which of the statements below is true for the bibliography section of a dissertation?
- It is a single list of all sources arranged alphabetically by the last name of the author, editor, or whoever is first in each entry.⁹**
 - It should have at least 100 entries.
 - It must not include references that the writer used in his paper.
 - It is a list of references consulted but not cited in the text.

⁷ James, *A Guide to Quantitative and Qualitative Dissertation Research*, 2.

⁸ European Commission, *English Style Guide: A handbook for authors and translators in the European Commission* (European Union, 2021), 18.

⁹ Kate, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations* 156.

10. A colon is often used to indicate that an expansion, qualification, quotation, or explanation is about to follow. Which of the following statements below is true?

- Do not use colons at the end of headings.
- In British usage, colons do not require the next word to start with a capital.
- Colons should be closed up to the preceding word, letter, or number.
- All the above.**¹⁰

¹⁰ European Commission, *English Style Guide for authors and translators in the European Commission*, 8.

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Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.